

**Kazakhstan's Health Economy
and Management
Author: Mariam Ohanyan**

*Deggendorf Institute of Technology
Master of Digital Health*

*"This research paper was originally prepared as part of the coursework requirements at
Deggendorf Institute of Technology, July, 2025*

Content list

1. General Economy: the main statistical indicators.....	3
2. Health Expenditure: various measures of health expenditure.....	4-5
3. Types and Financing sources.....	6
4. Health Services (primary, specialized, chronic, social, mental)	7-9
4.1. Primary health care (PHC)	
4.2. Specialized outpatient care	
4.3. Chronic diseases treatment	
4.4. Social health	
4.5. Mental Health	
5. Structure of Healthcare system: Ministry, Facilities and Workforce.....	10
6. Performance: Cost, Quality, Innovation.....	11-13
5.1. Cost	
5.2. Quality	
5.3. Innovation	
7. Current Challenges and Future Development.....	14
8. Summary: Conclusions and Recommendations.....	15
9. Appendixes.....	16-23
10. References	24-25

1. General Economy: the main statistical indicators

The Republic of Kazakhstan, is located mainly in Central Asia with part in Eastern Europe, with official languages Kazakh and Russian. The capital of country is Astana.

On the last years after 2000-s, it has had significant growth in many areas, as well as in economy, technology and IT industry.

The main demographic and economic indicators and statistics of the country, updated no later than in the 2th decade of 2025, and published by Bureau of National statistics Demographic and economic indicators are published by Strategic planning and reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan are shown (1).

Demographics:

Total population	20 353 265
Women	10 406 888
Men	9 946 377
Natural growth in 2025	80016
Migration balance in 2025	7257

Economy:

Consumer Price Index (CPI)	111,3%
IPV GDP: 105.6%	105,6%
GDP at current prices:	\$59,633.0
Short-term economic indicator	<i>108,6% (Compared to the same period of the previous year, January–May 2025)</i>
Goods turnover (mln \$)	29272,7
Real income index	103,0%
Total unemployment rate	4,6%

Healthcare:

Number of recipients of targeted social assistance	413,7
The number of doctors and specialists	83379
Number of pension recipients	2453
Number of hospital organizations	830
Physician density in the country	4,1 per 1,000 population

2. Health Expenditure: various measures of health expenditure

Based on The Global Economy report from 2021, where range of the country is based on the % of expenses form GDP (as less the % of expenses from GDP, as higher the range) in 2021 Kazakhstan was in 154 from 181 countries. It means that the country spent insufficient money to healthcare.

Another report, published by World Bank shows that expenditures of per person in Kazakhstan in 2022 was 1129 dollars and in 106th position among other countries (2).

As a comparison, neighbor countries had lower amount of expenses, f.e. Uzbekistan showed 716,39 dollars Turkmenistan only 873,35 dollars, Kyrgyz Republic 310, 74 so that expenses of Kazakhstan are near such countries as Ukraine, Moldova, China.

Detailed look gives more clearness on about expenditures in Kazakhstan. Based on government’s latest report in 2024 the expenditures on healthcare in Kazakhstan was to \$8.29 billion USD (3). The latest updated data gives results of expenses in the 1Q of 2025, and the amount was about 1,90 billion USD. If we compare 1Q of 2024 and 1Q of 2025, the number of expenditures increased about 15 %, but the final comparison can be done only by the end of year (4). Chart 1 detailed separation of expenditures in 2024, the amount, as well as percentage of each mean was:

Chart 1

Meanwhile, countries near the Kazakhstan had significantly different overall expenditures, which is described in Table 1.

Country	GDP (2024)	Healthcare expenditures	% from GDP
Kazakhstan	\$288 billion	\$8,29 billion	~2,5 %
Uzbekistan	\$115 billion	\$3,1 billion	~2,7 %
Turkemnistan	\$62 billion	\$3,9 billion	~6,3 %

Kyrgyz Republic	\$15 billion	\$0,39 billion	~2,6 %
-----------------	--------------	----------------	--------

Table 1

Based on this data we can see, that despite country has the was biggest amount of expenses, overall % of spent on healthcare is the less among those four mentioned countries, which can mean that healthcare may be a relatively lower priority in Kazakhstan's national budget, despite its stronger economy.

Some other indicators of healthcare expenditure in Kazakhstan, as well as changes and tendencies can be seen in the tables and diagrams published by WHO Global Health Expenditure Database (5).

Table 1. Key statistics in appendix 1 shows:

1. Health spending US\$ per capita (CHE) raised steadily: from \$140 (2005) to \$421 (2022).
2. Government domestic health spending has reached (% of total health spending)- 61,5% (2022)
3. Out-of-pocket spending was 30,9% (2022)
4. Priority to health (share of health in total government spending) 10,6% in 2022
5. GDP US\$ per capital Increased from \$3,577 (2005) to \$11,255 (2022)

The table shows, that Kazakhstan’s health expenditure per person is growing, and despite government is the main source of funding, but out-of-pocket costs are still high, which can impact in a negative way at availability and justice.

More graphs and statistics data can be seen in Appendixes 2-6.

3. Types and Financing sources

Healthcare in Kazakhstan can be categorized in the following way:

By funding source	Level of care	By Service Type
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guaranteed Volume of Free Medical Care • Compulsory Social Health Insurance • Out of Pocket 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary care • Secondary care • Tertiary care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency medical care • Outpatient care, Inpatient care • Rehabilitation and palliative care

Table 2

Based on E-gov of Kazakhstan, regarding the publication from 2022, there are several sources of financing in healthcare (6). The financial sources of health care in Kazakhstan are mentioned as:

1. Budget funds;
2. Assets of the social health insurance fund;
3. Funds of voluntary health insurance;
4. Funds received for the provision of paid services;
5. Voluntary donations;
6. Other sources

Based on WHO publication about 2022 health care sources, (appendix 2), the Kazakhstan's healthcare financing sources was separated in the below way:

1. Government spending (blue) -is the biggest source funder of healthcare;
2. Out-of-pocket expenditures (red) is the second largest source;
3. Contributions, according to the public health insurance (light Azure) only appear in the last few years (around 2020-2022), indicating the recent introduction of the National Insurance System;
4. Andonic advances (permanent), external CP (Green) and other resources (Purple) are very small proportions.

4. Health Services (primary, specialized, chronic, social, mental)

There is a free medical care, available for each citizen in Kazakhstan and provided by **guaranteed state benefit package (later in text - GSBP)**. Also, beginning from 2020, Kazakhstan has implemented to a Social Health Insurance (later in text- SHI) -based system, where the Social Health Insurance Fund (later in text- SHIF) consolidates public funds (including contributions from employers and employees) and purchases health services from public and private health care providers.

There are two benefits packages for publicly funded health services that complement each other: the state guaranteed benefits package and the SHI package, both of which are administered by the SHIF but with distinct funding pools.

The difference between the GSBP and Compulsory Social Health Insurance (later in text - CSHI) is that the GSBP is for the total population, despite their status in the health care system with a minimum social standard. The CSHI covers mostly consultative and diagnostic care, including high-cost lab services, outpatient drug provision beyond the GSBP, inpatient substitute and planned inpatient care, rehabilitation and remedial treatment.

The comprehensive list of essential healthcare services, available for population of Kazakhstan is publicly documented on the official government (7).

4.1. Primary health care (PHC)

Every citizen has access to primary health care. For using services of PHC, each citizen choose his outpatient hospital or clinic and doctor based on proximity to home, work, or study, with outpatient attachment allowed once a year. Primary healthcare is provided by rural and municipal centers.

The PHC includes the following medical services:

- Visit and examination by doctor or nurse;
- Emergency care provision;
- Laboratory and diagnostics;
- Prevention of chronic illnesses;
- Preparation for family planning and children birth;
- Medical rehabilitation in 3 stages

These services are the most widespread and needed, as they cover chronic and socially significant diseases prevention and care. Finally, the PHC facility is a way to access to specialized medical care for the attached population, which includes both outpatient services and inpatient hospitalization.

4.2. Specialized outpatient care

There is a number of free outpatient services that is a **guaranteed state benefit package and compulsory social health insurance**. Main of them are:

- Treatment by professionals: endocrinologists, cardiologists, gynecologists, etc.;
- Large number of tests: blood test, urine test, PCR, biochemical blood test, etc.;
- Diagnostic studies: ultrasound, mammography, endoscopy, etc.;
- Medical treatment procedures and manipulations: inhalations, phonophoresis, minor surgical interventions, casting, biopsy, etc.

4.3. Chronic diseases treatment

In accordance with regulation "On the health of the people and the healthcare system", patients with chronic diseases can count on following support: (8)

1. Dynamic monitoring is carried out to prevent complications, exacerbations of diseases, their prevention and medical rehabilitation in outpatient settings;
2. Accounting and monitoring is carried out by a multidisciplinary group, according to the conclusion of a PHC doctor;
3. Depending on the disease and diagnosis, dynamic monitoring is carried out by a specialized specialist or a PHC doctor;
4. Patients with chronic diseases are provided with medicines as part of outpatient drug provision

4.4. Social Health

4.4.1. Groups of population with social risk are children under 18 years of age; pregnant women; participants of the Great Patriotic War; disabled people of groups 1, 2, 3; mothers of numerous children; recipients of targeted social assistance; old-age pensioners; patients with infectious, socially significant diseases and diseases, posing a danger to others) in the direction of a specialist. Regarding to socially vulnerable categories of the population, there is no an exact regulating, which describes the available medical services for them. However, in the overall and general articles describing health system it is mentioned, that they have preferential terms and priority access to medical services in restricted cases.

4.4.2. Another category of social health, considering here, is a list of diseases, which need special social help. Examples of socially significant diseases are Tuberculosis, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), etc. (9)

Health services for those group of population is their treatment in outpatient conditions; inpatient conditions; hospital-substituting conditions and some medications. Basic medical services will be covered in scope of GSBP, however, further diagnostics, registration at a dispensary, and consultations with specialists are included in the CSHI package and require an insurance status. The whole list of socially significant diseases is in Appendix 7.

4.4.3. The third point in social healthcare field is the regulation about providing social services for the exact group of population, which is published in the main regulation about special social services in Kazakhstan (10):

Services include:

- Prevention of HIV infection;
- Inpatient care;

- Rehabilitation and medical rehabilitation;
- Palliative care and nursing care;
- Services for orphaned children;
- Children left without parental care from birth to three years old;
- Children with mental and physical disabilities from birth to four years old, providing psychological and pedagogical support to families at risk of abandoning a child

5.Mental Health:

Based on article published by Information and legal system of regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan (11), people with mental diseases, depending on their diagnosis, can get the following help:

1. In outpatient facilities that do not provide overnight medical supervision and treatment, including overnight admission of patients admitted to medical facilities;
2. In inpatient facilities that provide round-the-clock medical supervision, treatment, care and delivery of a bed at mealtimes, including in the case of "one-day" treatment, which is monitored around the clock on the first day after the start of treatment;
3. Bed replacement facilities that do not require daily medical supervision and treatment and ensure daily medical supervision and treatment by providing beds;
4. Other medical services

The mental diseases are more than 150, listed in this regulation. Examples of mentioned diseases are organic (affective) mood disorders, schizoaffective disorder, manic type, mixed obsessive thoughts and acts.

5. Structure of Healthcare system

Based on the updated statistics (1) there are 830 hospitals in Kazakhstan. Number of doctors is 83379 and mid-level healthcare professionals are about 191000.

Healthcare in Kazakhstan is managed by Ministry of Healthcare, which has 2 main committees (12):

1. Committee of Sanitary and epidemiological control

The Republican State Institution "Committee of Sanitary and Epidemiological Control of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan" is a subdivision of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which manages public health, sanitation, the epidemiological health of the population, control and supervision of compliance with the requirements created by technical regulations and standards bubbled documents.

2. Committee for medical and pharmaceutical control

The Republican State Institution "Committee for Medical and Pharmaceutical Control of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan" is an agency that oversees and executes state policy, as well as exercises government control and oversight in the areas of medical services, and the distribution of medicines and medical devices within its authority.

Departments of Ministry of Health are:

1. Internal audit Department of the Ministry of healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan;
2. Department of International Cooperation and Integration;
3. Department of Maternal and Child Health Protection;
4. Department of Corporate Governance of Subordinate Organizations and State Assets;
5. e-Health Development Department

The whole list of 9 departments can be found in the official web-site of Ministry of health.

Workforce structure of Ministry of Healthcare:

1. Alnazarova Akmaral Sharipbaevna: Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan;
2. Tokezhanov Bolat Turganovich: Head of the Staff of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan;
3. Sultangaziyev Timur Slamzhanovich: First Vice Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan;

The whole list of Vice-ministers can be found in the official web-site of Ministry of health.

6. Performance: Cost, Quality, Innovation

6.1. Cost

According to the regulation “On approval of tariffs for medical services provided within the framework of the guaranteed volume of free medical care and in the system of compulsory social health insurance”, the cost of medical service, provided for free and paid by government, takes into notice the several points:

- The base rate of 336,89 USD dollars
- Cost-intensity coefficients of each type of CPG;
- Correction factors;
- The coefficient of accounting for work allowances in rural areas;
- The coefficient of accounting for the duration of the heating season; environmental coefficient; in some cases, an academic coefficient, a scientific and innovative correction factor, and others.

Private medical clinics in Kazakhstan typically offer standard health services, such as general consultation and ultrasound diagnosis, at prices that are often comparable to those in the public sector. But patients are typically expected to pay more for greater convenience, shorter waiting times and more personalized care. Comprehensive diagnostic programs and premium check-up packages can range from about \$ 600 to \$ 1,300 or more, depending on the clinic and scope of the service. On the other hand, routine services such as general practitioner visits or basic ultrasounds typically cost between \$ 7 and \$ 25. Clinics that welcome international patients or offer English-speaking staff may apply slightly higher prices, reflecting both demand and the specialization of services.

6.2. Quality

According to statistics of CEOWORLD magazine, Kazakhstan has had rank of 78 between 101 countries with it’s quality of healthcare. Separated indicators of healthcare are (13):

Rank	Country	Medical Infrastructure and Professionals	Medicine Availability and Cost	Government Readiness	Health Care Index (Overall)
78	Kazakhstan	73,69	54,62	59,64	34,28

Table 3

The indexes show, that despite infrastructure and professional have a high estimation, but medicine availability and cost, as well as governance readiness are low, so that taking into account the impact of each one (the weight of each index) we see the low health care index.

Quality of healthcare in Kazakhstan is regulated by number of articles, as Article 15 "Joint Commission on the Quality of Medical Services", Article 138 "Requirements for the development of standards for the organization of medical care " (14).

According to a sociological study by the Institute of Public Policy, one in four Kazakhstanis (27.8%) complain about medical institutions or staff (29.1% are urban residents, 25.5% are rural residents).

The main reasons for complaints in % are given in Chart 2.

Chart 2.

Overall, the survey results show the following trends:

1. Middle-aged and older people are more likely to express dissatisfaction;
2. Women tend to complain more than men;
3. The frequency of complaints is higher among people with a lower level of education;
4. Citizens with lower incomes are more likely to complain;
5. The number of applications increases with the increase in the number of children in the family (15).

Taking into notice that at the current moment there is no any exact regulation or rule, standard which describes how exactly the quality of medical services should be estimated, there is a lot of work to do to implement such methodology., as well as collect a data and work on increasing of the quality of medical services for population.

6.3. Innovations

From the 1 of January 2019, in Kazakhstan the paper based health records were replaced to Electronic health passports for each citizen, which is available for them in the eGov mobile app. This means, the country has had a significant success in developing of digital technologies and electronic health records is one the first and strong steps (16).

In the recent decade, information technologies in healthcare and healthcare digitalization was one of the key areas of work. Some initiatives were organized for this, for example: the implementation of electronic medical records

- Telemedicine systems;
- Online consultations with doctors;
- Use of big data and artificial intelligence for processing and analyzing medical data;
- Electronic prescriptions and test results;

- Smart medical devices for health monitoring (17).

According to the regulation, on the website of Information and legal system of regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan the regulation about " On approval of the rules for the organization, provision and payment of remote medical services " was published.

According to that, remote medical services provided within the framework of the **GSBP** and (or) in the CSHI system are provided at the direction of the attending physician for the pre-medical medical care and primary health care; specialized, including high-tech; medical care and medical rehabilitation; palliative care (18).

The document also has detailed description of how the telemedicine services should be organized, how the control of treatment process should go, where and how patients can connect to doctors, check their personal data, as well as how those services should be paid, etc.

7. Current Challenges and Future Development

Based on National Development Plan of Kazakhstan until 2029, healthcare field needs a noteworthy change in the future years. The document gives a short overview of current situation and problems, as well as the key areas of development (19).

Key problems in the country required development and solution are:

1. Financing

In recent years, financing of healthcare under the compulsory social health insurance system in Kazakhstan has increased significantly, reaching 3,7% of GDP in 2023.%.

Despite the higher level of funding, problems persist, including lower levels of medical care that do not cover all costs or do not match inflation, which limits quality improvement and private sector participation.

2. Infrastructure and equipment

About 49,3% of medical institutions are dilapidated, 40% of them require major repairs. More than 35% are adapted premises, which limits the introduction of new technologies and the creation of the necessary conditions. Equipment wear is on average 66,3%, including medical – 49,1%, laboratory-83,5%.

3. Staff shortage

Gaps between urban and rural areas (3-7 times difference) and regions. Additionally, there is a significant shortage of mid-level medical staff, with exact number of 1,100 vacant doctor positions in rural areas.

4.The healthcare system relies on fragmented IT systems without integration, resulting in poor transparency and inefficiency. Insufficient digitalization hampers financial control and resource planning, resulting in overspending and inefficient use of funds.

The development of healthcare until will be focused on:

1. Strengthening the prevention of noncommunicable diseases and reducing mortality among the population;
2. Improving the healthcare financing system;
3. Improving the quality of medical care;
4. Increasing the availability of medical service

8. Summary: Conclusions and Recommendations

Kazakhstan has made tremendous progress in reforming its health system, but there are still significant problems that hinder fair and effective care. Public health spending remains below the global average, and direct payments continue to represent a significant portion of health care funding, making it difficult for low-income populations to access quality care. The unequal distribution of health care, especially in rural and remote areas, leads to inequalities in health care access and outcomes. To meet these challenges, Kazakhstan must commit to increasing public health funding to 4-5% of GDP, in line with international standards.

Expanding the coverage and access of primary health care services, especially outside major urban centers, is essential to improving health equity. Reducing direct payments through broader insurance coverage and government support can protect families from financial hardship. In addition, investing in Moderna infrastructure, medical technologies, and training and retaining health professionals will improve the quality of services and the sustainability of the system. Strengthening the governance framework, applying clinical standards, and ensuring transparency and accountability in health care spending are also essential steps to create a sustainable and inclusive health system that meets the needs of all citizens.

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Key Statistics

Key Statistics ☰ 🗨

	2005	2010	2015	2019	2022
Health spending US\$ per capita (CHE)	140	241	310	264	421
Government domestic health spending % Health spending (GGHE-D%CHE)	65.0%	67.4%	63.1%	59.9%	61.5%
Out-of-pocket spending % Health spending (OOPS%CHE)	34.4%	27.3%	32.1%	33.9%	30.9%
Priority to health (GGHE-D%GGE)	11.5%	8.2%	8.4%	8.3%	10.6%
GDP US\$ per capita	3,577	8,793	10,196	9,457	11,255

Appendix 2. Sources of Health Expenditure

Appendix 3. Current Health Expenditure

Current Health Expenditure (CHE%GDP and CHE per capita, US\$)

Appendix 4. Domestic Government Expenditure and OOPS

**Domestic Government Expenditure and OOPS
(GGHE-D%CHE and OOPS%CHE)**

Appendix 5. External aid and Health priority

Appendix 6. GDP and domestic government health

Appendix 7. List of socially significant diseases in Kazakhstan:

Disease	Codes of the International Classification of diseases
Tuberculosis	A15-A19
Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) Disease	B20-B24
Chronic Viral Hepatitis and Liver Cirrhosis	B18.0, B18.1, B18.2, B18.8, B19, K74
Malignant Neoplasms (including in situ and uncertain/unknown behavior)	C00-97; D00-09; D37-48
Diabetes Mellitus	E10-E14
Mental and Behavioral Disorders	F00-F99
Cerebral Palsy (Childhood Cerebral Paralysis)	G80
Acute Myocardial Infarction (first 6 months)	I21, I22, I23
Rheumatic Diseases	I00-I02; I05-I09; M12.3; M35.3
Systemic Connective Tissue Disorders	M30-M36
Degenerative Diseases of the Nervous System	G30-G32
Demyelinating Diseases of the Central Nervous System	G35-G37
Orphan (Rare) Diseases	B55, D56, D56.0-D56.2, D56.4, D57, D57.0-D57.2, D59.5, D61.9, D69.3, D76.0, D80-D84, E53.1, E74.0, E75.2, E76.0-E76.2, E80.2, E83.0, E84.8, E85.0, E88.0, G12.2, G35, G40.4, G93.4, J84, J84.0, J84.1, J84.8, J84.9, I27.0, K50, K51, L10, L13.0, M08.2, M30.3, M31.3, M31.4, M 31.8, M32.1, M33, M33.2, M35.2, Q78.0, Q80, Q81.

References

1. Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Bureau of National Statistics – main indicators. Published 2025.
<https://stat.gov.kz/>
2. World Bank. Current health expenditure per capita, PPP (current international \$) – Kazakhstan.
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.XPD.CHEX.PP.CD?locations=KZ>
3. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Financial and economic activities of healthcare organizations and social services in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Published 2024.
<https://stat.gov.kz/en/industries/social-statistics/stat-medicine/publications/409040/>
4. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan. General information about expenditures of 2025: data from 1st quarter. Report No. B-20-01-K (I 2025). Published 2025.
[https://stat.gov.kz/upload/iblock/0a4/y199b1iiga0no4n6a4xxzfbt56ycmq6m/%D0%92-20-01-%D0%9A%20\(I%202025\)%20%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B3%D0%BB.pdf](https://stat.gov.kz/upload/iblock/0a4/y199b1iiga0no4n6a4xxzfbt56ycmq6m/%D0%92-20-01-%D0%9A%20(I%202025)%20%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B3%D0%BB.pdf)
5. World Health Organization. Global Health Expenditure Database: Kazakhstan. Published 2023
<https://apps.who.int/nha/database>
6. Government of Kazakhstan. Health care financing. Electronic Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Published 2022.
https://egov.kz/cms/en/articles/public_health/Health-care-financing?mobile=no&ysclid=mby613olqd288319107
7. Government of Kazakhstan. State services and health information portal.
<https://www.gov.kz/article/171880?ysclid=mc3k92zcn3488751615>
8. Republic of Kazakhstan. On the health of the people and the healthcare system. IPS “Adilet”. Published 2022.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/K2000000360>
9. Republic of Kazakhstan. On the approval of the list of socially significant diseases. IPS “Adilet”. Published 2020.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2000021263#z14>
10. Republic of Kazakhstan. On the standard for the provision of special social services in the field of healthcare. IPS “Adilet”. Published 2023.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2300033545>

11. Republic of Kazakhstan. On the organization of medical and social assistance in the field of mental health. IPS "Adilet". Published 2020.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2000021712>
12. Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Organizational structure and leadership.
<https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/dsm/>
13. CEOWORLD Magazine. Countries with the best health care systems: 2024 rankings. Published May 5, 2024. <https://ceoworld.biz/>
14. Republic of Kazakhstan. Standardization of medical services. IPS "Adilet". Published 2023.
<https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/dsm/activities/2217?lang=ru&ysclid=mcg97cozcf529986818>
15. 716.kz. Analytics: How Kazakhstanis evaluate the quality of medical care. Published 2024.
<https://716.kz/news/35216-analitika-obraschenii-kak-kazahstancy-ocenivayut-kachestvo-medpomoschi.html>
16. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The launch of the electronic health passport. Published 2019.
<https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/dsm/press/news/details/38036?lang=ru&ysclid=mcxm4a1is708791896>
17. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Innovations in healthcare: Kazakhstan's path to quality medicine. Published 2025.
https://www.kt.kz/eng/government/reforms_and_innovations_in_2025_ministry_of_healthcare_1377972844.html
18. Republic of Kazakhstan. On the rules for the organization, provision and payment of remote medical services. IPS "Adilet". Published 2021.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2100022151>
19. Republic of Kazakhstan. National Development Plan of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2029. IPS "Adilet". Published 2024.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/U2400000611#z68>